

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

IMPROVING THE STABILITY OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES BASE D ON
NORMAL DISTRIBUTION AND CONTROL CHARTS

Ablazova Kamola Sakhbovna

PhD Candidate Faculty of Mathematics, Andijan State University, Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article analyzes the issues of stability, an important factor in product quality control, and its provision. It presents an asymmetry-excess mathematical model that determines the stability of technological processes modeled with a normal distribution, and reveals the importance of its practical use. Ensuring the quality of products produced in technological operations depends on such properties as the stability and stability of the technological processes determined over time. Ensuring them depends on improving the properties of the technological processes at specified times, such as accuracy and reproducibility. In the article, mathematical models are built based on the CCs found on the basis of the "Asymmetry-excess" ($a - \gamma$ CC) statistics, which check whether the density function of a one-dimensional normal number X maintains its standard form during sampling times (i.e., determines the stability of the PP). With these models, it is possible to analyze the stability of the technological processes. Using these models, the stability of the technological processes was analyzed using mathematical models based on $a - \gamma$ CCs, based on the data obtained to study problems in the welding and painting shops of an automobile plant.

Key words: normal distribution, technological process, stability, control chart, asymmetry, excess.

Introduction

Today, improving the quality of products while ensuring the stability of the technological process is one of the tasks of scientific and practical importance. The development of mathematical models, numerical algorithms and software tools designed to solve practical problems in this wide field of activity is an urgent issue. Such issues are being addressed by scientific and technical personnel in the industrialized countries of the world, including the USA, Japan, China, Germany, Korea, Great Britain, the Russian Federation and other countries, as urgent issues.

American scientists and practitioners such as U. Shewhart, E. Deming, D. Djuran, and others were engaged in research and development on solving problems of product quality management using statistical methods abroad. They achieved high results by using the control chart method in statistical quality assurance. Since these issues are related to the principle of statistical hypothesis testing, the works of scientists such as D. Neumann, E. Pearson, A. Fisher, and A. Wald can be used to construct control charts[4]. It should be noted that the theoretical and practical works of scientists such as A. N. Kolmogorov, Y. K. Belyaev, B. V. Gnedenko, L. N. Bolshev, N. V. Smirnov, D. Himmeloblauf, E. Shindovsky, O. Shyurts, R. Shtorm, B. Hansen, and G. Tagutu also made a great contribution to the development of this direction. Currently, the development of the control chart method and the increase in scientific and methodological work in this direction are greatly facilitated by the articles and books of such scientists as B. Woodall, Y. P. Adler, D. Montgomery, H. Y. Mittag, H. Rinne, V. A. Shper, S. F. Zhulinsky, M. Aslam, B. Costa, R. Quinino, D. Wheeler, D. Chambers. Therefore, the number of scientific works on the study of processes using control charts is increasing. The above problems

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

arose in our republic with the entry of joint ventures. To determine the stability of the technological process, these enterprises use ISO standards or standards of some countries.

In developed enterprises in the world, a large number of homogeneous products are produced. Several theoretical and practical models have been created to determine the stability of the technological process, aimed at improving the quality of such products. Currently, the improvement of the control chart model for studying the stability of technological processes, the development of numerical algorithms and software tools are among the urgent issues.

Methods

It is known that the stability of technological processes is understood as the property of a technological process that determines the reproducibility of the probability distribution of its parameters over a specified time interval without external intervention.[8]. By the stability of a technological process we understand the property of ensuring the accuracy of product quality parameters over time. [7].

The stability of a technological process is a general indicator of stability. [9] This figure 1.1 depicts the density function of the probability distribution of a parameter of a) stable technological process; b) unstable technological process.

Figure 1. a) stable technological process; b) unstable technological process.

The quality indicator of products produced in technological operations in technological processes depends on the stability of the technological process. In case a) in Figure 1, the share of quality products is high and the process is predictable, and in case b) the share of quality products is low and the process is unpredictable.

Currently, using the capabilities of science and technology, various software packages have been developed for statistical quality assurance and, in particular, for determining the stability of the technological process: CAQ (computer-aided quality assurance), PPS (production planning and control software package), etc. are examples. However, in real production, there are still losses due to the production of poor-quality products.[6]. The reason is that scientific and technological innovations, including statistical methods, have not been fully implemented in some enterprises.

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

In technological operations in a technological process, the products produced have different quality characteristics. Therefore, there is variation (dispersion). Historically, there are two principles for reducing this variation. The first is the engineering principle, in which products are divided into quality or poor quality products based on a certain standard. This principle continued from the idea of using parts interchangeably proposed by Eli Whitney in 1793 until 1924, when the American engineer and scientist W. Shewhart developed the principle of using statistical methods in statistical quality assurance. Historically, the first principle did not justify itself, poor-quality products continued to be produced and costs were high. W. Shewhart created a statistical instrument called control charts (CCs) that reduced variation and costs

Results

Suppose that the distribution of the numerical characteristic X , which determines the quality of the product obtained in technological operations in a technological process, obeys the normal law with parameters $\mu_0 = M(X); \sigma_0^2 = D(X): X \sim N(\mu_0; \sigma_0^2)$. In production, the parameters μ_0 and σ_0^2 are given as technical standards or are estimated based on initial samples when the technological process is under statistical control [3].

At unit times $t = 1, 2, \dots, l$, we take n instantaneous samples $\mathbf{X} = (x_{1t}, x_{2t}, \dots, x_{nt})$ from X . Here, X -represents one indicator of the product produced in the technological process, $x_{1t}, x_{2t}, \dots, x_{nt}$ denote the measurement results of X at a specified $t = 1, 2, \dots, l$ unit of time.

In technological operations, due to simple (random) or significant reasons, the process may deviate from a stable state (i.e., there will be a deviation from μ_0 and σ_0^2). In order to correctly assess the state of the technological process using statistical methods, it is necessary to check the state $X \sim N(\mu_0; \sigma_0^2)$ based on $\mathbf{X}, t = \overline{1}; \overline{l}$ samples[5]. In mathematical statistics, this is done by testing the following hypotheses at the α significance level:

$$H_0: P(X < x) = F(x; \mu_0; \sigma_0^2); H_1: P(X < x) \neq F(x; \mu_0; \sigma_0^2).$$

We define the sample mean \bar{X}_{nt} , the adjusted sample variance (S_{nt}^2), the sample skewness coefficient (a_{nt}), and the sample excess coefficient (γ_{nt}) based on the instantaneous samples \mathbf{X} taken from X at times $t = 1, 2, \dots, l$ as usual:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{X}_{nt} &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n X_{kt}; S_{nt}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^2; \\ a_{nt} &= \frac{1}{nS_{nt}^3} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^3; \gamma_{nt} = \frac{1}{nS_{nt}^4} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^4. \end{aligned}$$

$$S_{nt}^2 > LCL_a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\bar{\mu}_3^2}{a_{0,995}^2}} \text{ va } S_{nt}^2 < UCL_\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\mu}_4}{\gamma_{0,005}}} \tag{1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Bunda } \bar{\mu}_3 &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \mu_{3t}, \mu_{3t} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^3; \bar{\mu}_4 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \mu_{4t}, \\ \mu_{4t} &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^4. \end{aligned}$$

Let a_α and γ_α be the quantiles of the distributions a_n and γ_n , respectively, at the α value level. Let χ^2 - denote the $Ch\{* | n - 1\}$ distribution with $n - 1$ degrees of freedom.[10].

The mathematical model of technological process stability "Asymmetry-excess":

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

If the following relation holds for the samples $(X_{1t}, X_{2t}, \dots, X_{nt})$ at a given unit time $t = \overline{1; l}$, the technological process is stable:

$$S_{nt}^2 > LCL_a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\bar{\mu}_3^2}{a_{0,995}^2}} \text{ va } S_{nt}^2 < UCL_\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\mu}_4}{\gamma_{0.005}}} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{\mu}_3 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \mu_{3t}, \mu_{3t} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^3; \bar{\mu}_4 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \mu_{4t}, \mu_{4t} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (X_{kt} - \bar{X}_{nt})^4.$$

a- control chart boundary definition:

- 1) we generate instant samples at unit times $t = \overline{1; m}$ of the initial phase of production and determine \bar{X}_{nt} ;
- 2) we find μ_{3t} at moments $t = \overline{1; m}$;
- 3) we determine the arithmetic mean $\bar{\mu}_3$ of the found μ_{3t} values and obtain $\bar{\mu}_3^2$. We divide the result by the quantile $a_{0,995}^2$, take the cube root, and determine LCL_a and draw the lower limit of the control chart in the Cartesian coordinate system;

γ – determination of the CC limit:

- 4) Based on the data in 1), we determine μ_{4t} at moments $t = \overline{1; m}$;
- 5) The arithmetic mean of the found values is found to be $\bar{\mu}_4$ and the quantile $\gamma_{0.005}$ is taken as the square root, and we determine UCL_γ and draw the upper limit of the control chart in the Cartesian coordinate system;

Determining the values of S_{nt}^2 , which determine the stability of the technological process:

- 6) Now we take instantaneous samples from the production at $t = \overline{1; l}$ units of time and determine \bar{X}_{nt} ;
- 7) Based on the samples at $t = \overline{1; l}$ units of time, we find the values of S_{nt}^2 and determine their values in the Cartesian coordinate system;

Analyzing the stability of the technological process:

- 8) If the inequality $LCL_a < S_{nt}^2 < UCL_\gamma$ is valid in the resulting $a - \gamma$ double control chart diagram at $t = \overline{1; l}$ units of time, then the technological process is stable, otherwise it is unstable.

Below is a sample diagram of the mathematical model (1). In this case, the analysis of the stability of the technological process is presented in accordance with the figure.

Figure 2. $a - \gamma$ control chart mathematical model diagram.

In the figure, the points satisfying the above inequality (1) are marked with a blue dashed line, and those that do not satisfy it are marked with a red dashed line. The green line indicates a stable, and the red line indicates an unstable technological process. The upper figure indicates asymmetry, and the lower one indicates an excess state.

(1) the mathematical model is built based on theorems 1 and 2 below. In this case, the controlled quantity of the control card is $g(X_t) = S_{nt}^2$.

Theorem1[1].

$\alpha = 0,01$ and $H_0: P(X < x) = F(x; \mu_0; \sigma_0^2)$ when the hypothesis is valid, the lower control limit of the a -CC is equal to $LCL = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\bar{\mu}_3^2}{a_{0,995}^2}}$. And the a -control chart power function is equal to $G_a(\sigma_t) =$

$$P(S_{nt}^2 \leq LCL) = Ch \left\{ \frac{n-1}{\sigma_t^2} \sqrt[3]{\frac{\bar{\mu}_3^2}{a_{0,995}^2}} |n-1 \right\}$$

Theorem2[1].

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

$\alpha = 0,01$ and the hypothesis H_0 is valid, the control limits of the γ -control chart are $LCL = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\mu}_4}{\gamma_{0.995}}}$; $UCL = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\mu}_4}{\gamma_{0.005}}}$. The power function of the γ -control chart is $G_\gamma(\sigma_t) = P(S_{nt}^2 \geq UCL) = 1 - Ch\left\{\frac{n-1}{\sigma_t^2} \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\mu}_4}{\gamma_{0.005}}} | n - 1\right\}$

Conclusions

The scientific results obtained in the article are based on the fact that the data obtained for the study of problems in the welding shop of UZ Auto Motors JSC during the operation of controlling the gap between two panels and in the painting shop during the priming of the car body were checked for normality (i.e., determining the stability of the technological process) using $a - \gamma$ control chart models, and positive results were obtained. In [2], mathematical models were built based on control charts found on the basis of Kolmogorov or Kolmogorov-Smirnov type statistics. These control chart models ensure the stability of the technological process.

The mathematical models developed are of theoretical and practical importance. They can be used to ensure the stability of the technological process. This, in turn, will allow improving the quality of products produced during technological operations in the technological process.

REFERENCES:

1. Ablazova K.S. Some control chart based on the consent criteria. // International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science. – Philadelphia, 2019. – №11. – P. 23-28. (№5; Impact Factor ISI=0.8).
2. Ablazova K.S. On a statistical control of a technological process described by a two-dimensional normal distribution. // International Journal of Statistics and Applied Mathematics. – India, 2020. – №5(4). – P.131-134. (№12; IF=5.34).
3. Ablazova K.S «On statistical tools-new control charts that ensure the stability of technological processes», // International conference "Contemporary mathematics and its applications", Uzbekistan 2021, November 19-21, C.128.
4. Akhmedov S.A. Statistical Process Control. Methodical guide. Andijan. -2005. B. 100.
5. Ablazova K.S. About the stages of determining the share of defects in the technological operations of the factory by statistical methods. // Republican scientific conference with the participation of "Sarymsakovskie chteniya". Tashkent. - 2021. - S. 312-314.
6. Shewhart W. A, "Statistical Methods from the Viewpoint of Quality Control," – N.Y, Dover Publications, Inc., (republished). (1939/1986), pp. 1-160.
7. Adler Yu.P., Maksimova O.V, Shper V.L., "Shewhart's control charts in Russia and abroad: a brief overview of the current state (statistical aspects)," Journal Standards and Quality vol.8, pp. 1-40, 2011. <https://baguzin.ru/wp/adler-i-dr-kontrolnye-karty-shuharta-v/>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

8. Mittag J, Rinne H, "Statistical methods of quality assurance," Moscow: Engineering, 1995, pp. 1-612.
9. Donald W, David Ch, "Statistical Process Control: Business Optimization Using Shewhart's Control Charts," M
10. Bolshev L, Smirnov N, "Mathematical statistics tables," Moscow: Science, 1983, pp. 1-416.

